

>>What is the Fibonacci Pressure doing now?

In this letter:

→ Small update from publishing on [MIMS 2.1.212b](#)

MIMS 2.1.212c - Fibonacci Pressure Fibonacci Cycles

When does “reversal” happen?

January 2022

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Re: What happens if “fibonacci pressure” meets another Fibonacci?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

Chart for BTF 20 D 1h printed on 1/24/22, 5:13 PM

Figure 1 - BTF following the OLD fibonacci, and once dipping below new fan, surging up to old fan line. Credit: author/Thinkorswim

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Figure 2 (above) - On 1/24 a new Fibonacci cycle was confirmed with bottom; the following day 1/25 the curve was reacting as predicted. Would this continue after the crossing on the 27th at 7am? (prediction)

Figure 3 - BTF at 12 pm 1/27; the futures price fell, as expected due to dropping volume and low market sentiments, and did so between 1/26 6pm and 1/27 4am; Fan pressure pushes back. Next spiral encounter (with fan): 1/28 6am; the author predicts a stalling fall, but continued downward pressure out til at least February.

Sincerely,
 Sf. R.
 Careaga